

Reconsidering a Source of Sir David Lyndsay's *The Monarche* and Its Significance In the Early Scottish Apocalyptic Tradition

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Abstract

Parallel to the distinctive character of Reformation in Scotland, the Protestant apocalyptic tradition in this country showed an original, nationalist-oriented style, defining itself against both English and French tendencies. Among the first texts to ground these differences was Sir David Lyndsay's *Dialog betuix Experience and ane Courteour off the Miserabyll Estait of the World*, commonly known as *The Monarche* (1552). Following the main themes of medieval eschatology, *The Monarche* incorporates key elements that will be characteristic of Protestant apocalypticism in Scotland and shows the influence of *Carion's Chronicle*, one of the most significant millenarian treatises in the Renaissance. This article analyzes the apocalyptic dimension of *The Monarche* and pays special attention to the particular circumstances surrounding Lyndsay's reception of *Carion's Chronicle*. By examining the connections between this poet and certain Scottish exiles in Eastern Europe, we aim to shed new light on the introduction of apocalyptic thought in Scotland and revise the traditionally accepted relationship between this text and similar treatises, such as *The Complaynt of Scotlande* or John Knox's earliest writings.

Keywords: David Lyndsay, *The Monarche*, apocalyptic, Scottish reformation

INTRODUCTION

In spite of early attempts to differentiate the Scottish Protestant tradition from English and Continental influences, there was actually very little distinction between them. Until 1560, the Reformation in Scotland and England shared similar doctrines and practices and any discrepancies that were highlighted were mainly to foster a sense of nationalism (MacDonald 2022). Though the initial causes of the change may have been different (more political in England, more religious in Scotland), the two nations quickly came together under a shared religion.

Undeniably, however, apocalypticism was one of the areas where their resistance achieved a remarkable degree of importance. The profound influence of Scottish apocalyptic thought played a significant role in creating a divide between England and France, due to the unique eschatological traditions that are native to both countries (Drinnon 2012: 18-62). In contrast, England continued to be greatly influenced by the teachings of Wyclif, who rejected the traditional interpretation of the Apocalypse that had already been abandoned in other parts of Europe (Ball 1975; Firth 1979). By contrast, France embraced Calvin's *laissez-faire* attitude and intentionally chose to distance itself from the increasing anticipation of an apocalyptic event that was spreading among millenarian groups throughout Europe. Subsequently, the long-standing Scottish practice bears a striking resemblance to Lutheran doctrines, yet with a progressive outlook that makes it stand out from the crowd (Gribben 2009).

One of the first individuals to contribute to the debate on the apocalyptic view of Scotland and its place in history was David Lyndsay. Sir David Lyndsay of the Mount, probably the most popular court *makar* under James V's reign, served for years as personal attendant to the king and played a crucial role in his education and mentorship. At the young age of twenty-two, Lyndsay began serving the Stewart family and from then on, his life was deeply connected to the turbulent history of the Scottish Crown during this period. The Flodden campaign, the uncertain period of James' childhood rule, his sudden rise to power with the king's endorsement, and the chaos that followed his passing were all significant events in his eventful life (Murion 1938; Edington 1994). Being well-acquainted with Gavin Douglas and William Dunbar, his remarkable genius and prolific output enabled him to achieve the highest acclaim in Scottish poetry until the 19th century, particularly with his creations such as *The Dreame*, *The Historie of Squyer Meldrum*, and his masterpiece *Ane Satyre of the Thrie Estatis*.

His final composition, titled *Ane dialog betuix Experience and ane Courteour, concerning the Disastrous Condition of the Warld*, commonly known as *The Monarchie*, has been thoroughly examined by scholars (Edington 1994; McGinley 2005; Tapscott 2016). Although some admire it as his most sophisticated and comprehensive poem, others consider it excessively long and repetitive, lacking the excellence

shown in *The Thrie Estatis*. In any case, the strong moralistic atmosphere and the complex historical context have led to a lack of academic attention on this poem, which researchers seem to overlook in favor of the more captivating realm of court sycophants, monarchs, and plebeians in Lyndsay's other satires.

The Monarche is divided into four separate books, with an Epistle, a Prologue, and an Exhortation to bookend it. Within its lines, a young courtier, burdened by the lack of effective government in Scotland and fearful of divine punishment for moral decay, encounters an elderly man named Experience who shares his concerns but expresses them with a pessimistic view of life. When asked about the origin of evil in the kingdom, Experience provided a comprehensive explanation based on the "laik of Faith, and for Ydolatrie, / For Fornicatioun, and for Adultrie, / Off Princis, Prelatis, with mony ane man & wyve" (ll. 67-9). In order to prove his point, Experience carefully recalled the histories of the most powerful empires (the Assyrian under King Ninus; the Persian under King Cyrus; the Greek in the time of Alexander; and the Roman Empire under Caesar's rule) and showed how God utilizes autocrats and calamities to bring about His divine plans. In the midst of these disasters, the Papacy and the deteriorated state of the Roman Church are considered the new oppressive rule, the so-called Fifth Monarchy, which is believed to eventually lead to the arrival of the Antichrist and the subsequent end of the world.

Taking into consideration the question of theodicy, Experience provides an overview of the most popular eschatological themes of the time. This includes a thoughtful exploration of the Four Last Things, a portrayal of the Antichrist (identified as the Pope), an outline of the Fifteenth Signs before the Doomsday, and ultimately a description of the End of the World. With that, the courtier goes back to his abode to reflect upon the futility of worldly matters and the importance of acquiescing to attain salvation.

Clearly, *The Monarche* addresses the deepest concerns of a poet who was losing their position at court and whose religious convictions had been affected by the decline of trust in the Catholic Church and a feeling of hopelessness during the Protestant Reformation. With sharp and biting satire, Lyndsay exposes the misconduct of political leaders and the corruption in Rome. Through this, he conveys a heartfelt plea for moral and spiritual transformation, emphasizing the urgency of the situation: "Gett upe, thow slepist all to lang, O Lorde, / And mak one hais-tie reformatioun." (ll. 2701-2) or "On to the deth, and steruit on the Rude, / Lat ws, O Lorde, be purgit with that blude." (ll. 6237-8). His millennialist outlook is the result of carefully studying history as a perpetual series of mistakes and a deep lack of faith in humanity, which consistently ignores past errors. The opposition between the openness of the courtier and the intense disillusionment of Experience presented by Lyndsay gives one of the most intimate and honest examples of apocalyptic discourse during the early Reformation.

APOCALYPTIC IMAGERY IN *THE MONARCHE*

In his unique and personal style, Lyndsay's apocalyptic writing incorporates elements inspired by some of the main medieval eschatological works. Some examples include the Fifteen Signs before Doomsday, directly taken from Jacobus de Voragine's *Legenda aurea* (ch. I "De Adventu Domini". Graesse 1850: 6-7) and a portrayal of the Antichrist influenced by Adso de Montier's *Libellus de Antichristo*. However, he also incorporates certain aspects from the new Protestant tradition that moved away from the medieval millenarianism rooted in the original paleo-Christian eschatological writings. For example, the denial of Purgatory, the identification of the Pope with the Antichrist (not founded on Rev. 13), or the prophetic interpretation of past events were interconnected with Reformed apocalypticism during that time, despite all three concepts having originated in Catholicism (Drinnon 2013). Nevertheless, the clearest evidence of Protestant influence in Lyndsay's work can be seen in his heavy reliance on *Carion's Chronicle*, which is widely regarded as the most significant contribution to eschatological thought during the Renaissance period (Stewart 1972: 272).

At the beginning of the Reformation, the apocalyptic textual tradition relied on three main components, two of which were already prominent in medieval theology: *the Book of Daniel* and *the Book of Revelation*. The third of the predictions was *the Prophecy of Elijah*, a revised edition of a Talmudic excerpt, which was most remarkably distinguished by its timeline of world history. It has been suggested that God's creation of the world would take a total of 6000 years, divided into three distinct periods of 2000 years each: the first period, *ante legum*, occurred before Moses journeyed out of Egypt; the second period, *sub lege*, took place while the Jewish Law was in effect; while the third period, *sub gratia*, falls within the era of Christ's grace. It was believed that the Second Coming will happen at the end of this third period (Reeves 1969). Contemporary intellectuals completely avoided accepting the belief in an approaching end time and strongly rejected the idea of the two thousand years leading up to it (Kugel 2003: 36). Most Protestant spiritual leaders, including Martin Luther, were expecting the Parousia to happen before the early 17th century according to this version of the *translatio imperii* motif. They believed that it would happen because of the actions of the newly appointed Antichrist, i.e., the Pope, and the modern armies of Gog and Magog, which referred to the Ottoman Empire (Firth 1979: 170). By their actions, the successor to the Roman Empire, Christendom, would be defeated, resulting in the initiation of Armageddon and the End of the World. *The Monarchie*, following this periodization, states that "so remanis to cum, but weir, / Four hundreth, with sew-in and fourtye yeir" (ll. 5302-3), predicting the End for the year 2000 of that third period. In Book Four of Lyndsay's poem, there is a detailed description of the history of the world spanning six millenia before the final Rapture (Lerner 1984).

Another crucial aspect of *The Prophecy of Eliah* was the vision of the Four Monarchies, which is an expanded version of Daniel's prophecy of the four beasts. This vision provides a narrative of the four empires that had already been described by Lyndsay throughout his poem. During the Renaissance, a new monarchy, known as the Fifth Monarchy, was introduced to justify the imminence of the Final Advent of Christ. Various royal lineages were recognized as such during the 16th century: the Spanish Empire, the Turks, the Muslims, or, as proposed by Sir David Lyndsay, the Papacy, were all seen as the catalysts of the apocalypse and were therefore highly regarded (Capp 1972).

CARION'S CHRONICLE AND THE MONARCHE

In the year 1531, the Dutch mathematician Johann Carion employed *The Prophecy of Eliah* as the basis for his well-known *Chronica*, a condensed compilation of prophecies taken from the Bible and other ancient sources, thereby providing a validation for the practice of utilizing astronomy to forecast future occurrences (Green 2011: 59). In the chronicle, a unitarian vision of time under the divine will was presented, continuing the allegorical interpretation of history that had been initiated by St Augustine and that was highly appreciated by Protestant theology. After a period of twelve months had elapsed, Philip Melanchthon thoughtfully revised and considerably broadened the *Chronicle*, largely disregarding the complex astronomical aspect and incorporating data from both biblical and patristic sources. Undoubtedly, it was Melanchthon's altered version of the *Chronicle* that became the strongly authoritative, nearly sacrosanct, text in Protestant tradition (even though it was preserved in history under the name of Carion) (Lotito 2019). Luther, who had previously been highly dubious of the prognostications of the end of the world, eventually transformed into one of the most passionate proponents of this treatise and his most recent compositions evidence the profound impact the *Chronicle* had upon him (Stewart 1972: 273).

Carion's influence on *The Monarchie* is widely recognized, evident in its overall structure, which is based on the Four Monarchies vision. Additionally, the inclusion of both apocalyptic and non-apocalyptic prophecies throughout the piece contributes to its significance. Lyndsay explicitly alludes to "the Chronicle" on no fewer than five occasions, and we can easily recognize more than a dozen direct quotations that have been extracted from that source. Rarely does Lyndsay differ in opinion from Carion, but when this happens, he presents both perspectives to allow the spectators to form their own judgment. No one has questioned this relationship, even though it is still unclear how Lyndsay could have been involved with this tradition (Stewart 1972: 274).

Carion's Chronicle was first translated into English by John Funck in 1550 (let us bear in mind that the publication date of *The Monarchie* is 1552) which could be an acceptable date to support a reliable transmission reception under normal circumstances, but that is not the case here. Katharine Firth (1979: 18) argues that the *Chronicle* went unnoticed in England for a long period of time because it presented a perspective of history that was based on factual information. That aspect was not something that the nation was accustomed to when it came to concepts of eschatological anticipation, so Carion's narrative would have been almost blasphemous to the English audience. It is impossible to determine with certainty whether this text would have been able to reach Scotland in less than three years, as Douglas Hamer suggests (1936: III.442), but there are some clues which point to the possibility that the origin of *The Monarchie* may have be traced back to 1549 (Edington 1994: 64), or that Lyndsay had knowledge of the *Chronicle's* outlines before that time. The play *Ane Satyre on the Thrie Estaitis*, written in 1551, gives some clear but somewhat scattered indications of his familiarity with Carion at that time and it seems evident that certain aspects of John the Commonweal's critique of Roman judicial corruption and parts of the initial explanation of Divyne Correctioun about the abuses of the kingdom are very similar to the *Chronicle*. Likewise, *Ane Dialogue betuix Experience and ane Courteour*, published in 1554 but probably sketched much earlier, directly mentions the *Chronicle* in its *ars moriendi* passage (Ruys 2013: 258). However, it is unlikely that Lyndsay had access to a copy of Funck's version of the text. Bearing in mind that Lyndsay was unable to decipher Melanchthon's original text in German, and that no other translations had been made prior to that, it is hard to believe that the initial encounter our poet experienced with the tradition was through a written form of the *Chronicle*. Alisdair Stewart's argument (1972: 273) that Lyndsay obtained the text (likely Funck's version) while he was in the process of composing the poem is not quite convincing even though it would explain why the majority of references to the source material are found in the last two books and the closing Exhortation. However, an analysis of the design and composition of the poem reveals that Lyndsay was familiar with the ins and outs of the *Chronicle* from its first inception, yet maybe, only at the final stages of the process of redaction, did he come to possess a written copy of the treatise.

The question that arises in the face of this rush of dates is, where did Lyndsay obtain these predictions and beliefs if he could not have access to a copy of *Carion's Chronicle* before starting *The Monarchie*?

By the time the poem was first written, there were only two documents in Scotland that clearly contained remnants of *Carion's Chronicle*. The first noteworthy work was *The Complaynt of Scotlande*, written by an unknown Scot named Wedderburn, Vicar of Dundee, in 1549. In that work, Wedderburn strongly

advocated for a union with France in the context of the crisis provoked by the “Rough Wooing” conflicts. The treatise, in fact, consists primarily of a mix of political dissent and commonplace imaginative prophecies for the future of the nation, such as Thomas of Erceldoune or Merlin’s, that predicted the downfall of Scotland’s enemies, which would be completed during the Last Judgment (Flood 2013: 174). After evaluating multiple chronologies to determine the date of the event, the author ultimately concluded that *The Prophecy of Elijah*, which is known to last for six millennia, was the most appropriate choice. The reference provided is too brief to be considered valid and in no other part of *The Complaynt* are there any other references to the monarchies or the Antichrist, but it is likely that Wedderburn was a Catholic, a fact that suggests that David Lyndsay could hardly be influenced by *The Complaynt*.

On the other hand, John Knox’s famous *First Public Address*, delivered at St Andrews shortly after the Passover of 1547, further confirms the validity of the *Chronicle*. As a consequence of being persecuted for his involvement in the Cardinal Beaton affair, Knox sought refuge in the Castle of St Andrews where, after careful consideration, he eventually overcame his initial reluctance to enter the ministry. In the opening chapter of his work *The Historie of the Reformatioun of Religioun within the Realm of Scotland* (1559-1566), the author recounts his experience of delivering his first sermon in the parish church of the Castle to a small crowd, possibly including Sir David Lyndsay, though it is impossible to know whether the Scottish poet was present or not among the audience. In the beginning of the speech, the prophecy of the Four Monarchies was mentioned; the reason was not to highlight God’s supernatural influence in human history, but rather to showcase the unwavering strength and endurance of the Israelite people, so that’s why the warnings of Doomsday found in *Carion’s Chronicle* were purposely ignored, and any prophecies about the end of the world mentioned in the sermon were taken from the *Book of Daniel* and the *Book of Revelation* in the Bible (Firth 1979: 113-131). Although Knox was evidently well acquainted with the *Chronicle*, yet it appears he was more engrossed in its illustrative and narrative qualities than in its prophetic message. Concerning his apocalyptic thought, as Richard Kyle states, “the Scottish reformer was first and foremost a man of the Bible” (1984: 449) and nowhere else than in the Scripture shall we find the fundamentals of his millenarian faith. Knox strongly emphasizes the cautionary nature of the apocalyptic writings, rather than focusing on their ability to predict the future. This is why his treatises have been classified as prophetic instead of apocalyptic by most scholars. It is difficult to determine the exact details of that sermon, because the only existing record is a lengthy description written twelve years later, but it makes unlikely to consider the sermon as the true origin of *The Monarchie*. It is unclear also whether Lyndsay and Knox had a chance to encounter

inside the castle, or even if the poet was a bystander to the speech, so there exist too many indeterminacies to assume that the start of *The Monarche's* apocalyptic design can be traced back to the parish kirk of St. Andrews.

This ambiguity allows us to propose a different hypothesis for this question. During the final years of James V's reign and beyond, David Lyndsay served as a Royal messenger, rather than a diplomat, carrying out various tasks for foreign courts. His activities were limited to small diplomatic interactions, though these trips allowed him to become familiar with political matters, which would later prove to be necessary after James's death (Williams 1996: 201). During one of his last expeditions, in the Winter of 1548, Lyndsay was sent to Denmark to negotiate a formal agreement with the Danish monarchy on the subject of the ongoing hostilities with England. Despite Lyndsay's best efforts, the request ultimately ended in failure, though eventually he was able to achieve a relatively peaceful accord with King Christian III regarding the pirates' raids in the North Sea (Chalmers 1806: 36).

Given the bad weather, his journey back was postponed until late Spring of 1549, resulting in him having to stay in Copenhagen for five to six months. Not a great deal is known regarding his sojourn in Denmark, but Thorkild Christensen, in his essay on the Scottish expatriates in Denmark in the 16th century (1970: 137), does allude to the fact that David Lyndsay would have encountered a circle of religious dissenters from Scotland who would have taught him the fundamentals of Danish Lutheranism. The person leading that community was *Dr Maccabæus*, that was not a real name but merely the pseudonymous of John MacAlpine, as Thomas M'Crie, the famous biographer, was able to reveal more than three centuries after (1855: 349). As documented in the *Corpus Reformatorum* (1836: III.771), MacAlpine was a former member of the Dominican Order who fled to England after being summoned to Perth to face charges of heresy. Living in London for three years, he was unfortunately forced to leave the country because of Henry VIII's Reaffirmation of the Six Articles in 1539 and eventually settled in Germany where he enrolled at the University of Wittenberg. There he registered for classes taught by Melanchthon, who was Professor of Divinity, and even participated in some *quodlibetal* disputations with him and Luther himself (Greaves 2004). Eventually, he obtained his doctorate in 1542 and also received his new Christian name, *Maccabæus*, in a ceremony presided by Luther. Recommended by his schoolmaster, MacAlpine accepted King Christian III's offer to become the Chair of Theology at the University of Copenhagen where he worked diligently until his death in 1557. During the later stages of his life, he became a prominent contributor to the growth of the Protestant Church in Denmark and actively participated in the translation of Luther's Bible into Danish.

It is possible that John MacAlpine may be the final, crucial piece of the puzzle researchers of Lyndsay have been seeking for decades. Lyndsay's six-month long stay alongside one of the disciples of Melanchthon, the famous Protestant prophet and the actual writer of the Lutheran rendition of *Carion's Chronicle*, appears to be a reliable explanation to connect the author of the Scottish poet to *The Prophecy of Elijah*. A complete version of the *Chronicle*, along with the study of Melanchthon's *Loci Communes Theologici*, could have introduced Lyndsay to the European apocalyptic tradition and the Four Monarchies legend, giving him the necessary elements to create *The Monarchie*. Growing increasingly concerned with eschatological themes, it is easy to envisage Lyndsay profoundly astounded by *Maccabæus'* teachings concerning Carion's chronological macrocosm and Melanchthon's prospective interpretations of past events.

CONCLUSION

Lyndsay's connections with MacAlpine and the Danish dissenters may not be crucial in understanding *The Monarchie*, as we already knew that Carion's *Chronicle* was the main source of the poem. The point of contact between the original source of the treatise and the author is hardly relevant to the final result, especially in such a composite work where the accumulation of apocalyptic textual traditions could be traced to countless works in Christian wisdom literature. However, it could shed light on the poet's unique understanding and interpretation of apocalypse, prophecy, and history during his mature years. It may also reveal his ultimate vision of Scotland, a nation whose behavior he had been criticizing since his earliest poems. His perspective of a nation destined to be condemned to "mortall miserie" (l. 64) under its leaders, fated to the same finale as the four dynasties mentioned in the *Chronicle*, allows the possibility of reform that is quite in line with Carion's work. The apocalyptic tenor, which for more than 6000 lines will be relentless with kingdoms such as Babylon, Persia, Greece or Rome, and which seems equally severe with the imminent destruction of Scotland, grows more contentious in the anticipation of an optimistic reform that would postpone the Parousia: "Expell the cause, than the effect belyue / Sall cease: quhen that the peple doith repent, / Than God sall slak his bow, quhilke yit is bent." (ll. 70-72). The perspective Lyndsay proposes at the beginning of his work, which aligns with what he had learned directly from Carion, is not apocalyptic, but rather apocalypticist, according to Bernard McGinn's classical definition: "[apocalypticism is the] sense of the imminence, or nearness of the end - the urgency that sets it apart from other eschatology - and can be psychological as much as chronologically exact, a sense of living in the shadow of the End and being driven by the final events" (1998: xvii and xx). The final result of the of Scotland's nation (and the rest

of the world) is still contingent, displaying an Augustinian perspective of history that interconnects the past, present, and future towards the ultimate End.

So far, it has been widely acknowledged that Lyndsay most certainly adopted his apocalyptic viewpoint directly from John Knox, especially the model of the cyclical evolution of history (Greaves 1976: 45; Firth 1979: 119). However, Knox's framework of prophetic history was fully developed during his exile years (from 1554 to 1559) after *The Monarchie* was finished and published (Edington 1994: 201; Kyle 1984: 450). Sir David Lyndsay's development of the apocalyptic imaginary along *The Monarchie*, seems more aligned with a non-chiliastic historical reformism, as we can observe in other Nordic countries, Denmark being specifically one of them (Skovgaard-Petersen 1998). We would therefore be in the presence of a third approach, far removed, of course, from the avowed millenarianism later propagated by John Napier, of interweaving historical reform with latter-day expectations of an imminent End.

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Ponovno preučevanje vira knjige *The Monarche* sira Davida Lyndsayja in njenega pomena v zgodnjem škotskem apokaliptičnem izročilu

Vzporedno z izrazitim značajem reformacije na Škotskem je protestantsko apokaliptično izročilo v tej državi razvilo izviren, nacionalistično usmerjen slog, ki se je opredeljeval tako proti angleškim kot francoskim težnjam. Med prvimi besedili, ki so utemeljila te razlike, je bil *Dialog betuix Experience and ane Courteour off the Miserabyll Estait of the World* sira Davida Lyndsayja, splošno znan kot *The Monarche* (1552). Sledi glavnim temam srednjeveške eshatologije in vključuje ključne elemente, ki so značilni za protestantsko apokaliptiko na Škotskem, ter kaže vpliv Carionove *Kronike*, enega najpomembnejših milenarističnih traktatov v renesansi. Članek analizira apokaliptično razsežnost knjige *The Monarche* in posveča posebno pozornost posebnim okoliščinam Lyndsayjeve recepcije Carionove kronike. S preučevanjem povezav med tem pesnikom in nekaterimi škotskimi izgnanci v Vzhodni Evropi želi avtor članka na novo osvetliti uvedbo apokaliptične misli na Škotskem in revidirati tradicionalno sprejeto razmerje med tem besedilom in podobnimi traktati, kot so *The Complaynt of Scotlande* ali najzgodnejši spisi Johna Knoxa.

Ključne besede: David Lyndsay, *The Monarche*, apokaliptika, škotska reformacija